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JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILDREN'S EMOTIONAL STATES IN SUCCESS AND FAILURE SITUATIONS DEPENDING ON HUBRISTIC MOTIVATION

The article presents the results of the study of emotional states of pupils of junior school age with different levels of development of hubristic motivation in situations of success and failure in game and educational activities. It is determined that the dominance of the aspiration for superiority activates the state of pride and envy in situations of failure, as well as the greater manifestation of positive states in a situation of praise in educational activity. A high degree of hubristic motivation in general contributes to more positive emotional states in situations of victory in a competition or a game.

Keywords: situations of success and failure, emotional states, junior school age, hubristic motivation, aspiration for perfection, aspiration for superiority.

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ПСИХОЕМОЦІЙНІ СТАНИ МОЛОДШИХ ШКОЛЯРІВ У СИТУАЦІЯХ УСПІХУ ТА НЕВДАЧІ В ЗАЛЕЖНОСТІ ВІД РІВНЯ ГУБРИСТИЧНОЇ МОТИВАЦІЇ

У статті показані результати дослідження емоційних станів учнів молодшого шкільного віку з різним рівнем розвитку губристичної мотивації у ситуаціях успіху та невдачі в ігровій та навчальній діяльності. Визначено, що домінування прагнення до переваги активізує стани гордості та заздрості у ситуаціях невдачі, а також більш прояв більш позитивних станів у ситуації похвали у навчальній діяльності. Висока міра губристичної мотивації загалом сприяє більш позитивним емоційним станам у ситуації перемоги в конкурсі чи грі.

Ключові слова: ситуації успіху та невдачі, емоційні стани, молодший шкільний вік, губристична мотивація, прагнення до досконалості, прагнення до переваги.

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ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ В СИТУАЦИЯХ УСПЕХА И НЕУДАЧИ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ УРОВНЯ ГУБРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ МОТИВАЦИИ

В статье показаны результаты исследования эмоциональных состояний учащихся младшего школьного возраста с разным уровнем развития губристической

мотивації в ситуаціях успіха і невдачі в ігровій і навчальній діяльності. Визначено, що домінування прагнення до переважності активізує стани гордості і заздрості в ситуаціях невдачі, а також більше проявлення позитивних станів в ситуації похвали в навчальній діяльності. Висока ступінь губристическої мотивації в цілому сприяє більш позитивним емоційним станам в ситуації перемоги в конкурсі або грі.

Ключові слова: ситуації успіха і невдачі, емоційні стани, молодший шкільний вік, губристическа мотивація, прагнення до досконалості, прагнення до переважності.

Introduction. The study of mental states of subjects of educational activity is of special importance for psychological science. Mental states act as qualitatively homogeneous manifestations of all psychic components in a certain period of time and act as a unity, integrity of all psychic elements, which is relative stability, endowed with a special structure, content. Mental states express the degree of activity of the functioning of the human psyche. They show the intensity of the course and the modality (quality) of mental processes and properties [1].

In general, mental states reflect everything that is happening in the period of time the peculiarities of the course of cognitive, emotional-volitional and individual psychological processes [1]. Mental states are not only internal processes, painted in one way or another emotional tone and manifested in the external actions, but also affect the course of activity, therefore, have a significant role in the flow of educational activities of schoolchildren.

Mental states are relatively new and not well-known categories. The study of the problem of mental states is presented in psychological research of L.M. Balabanova, I.V. Volzhentseva, V.A. Hansen, L.G. Wild, M.A. Kuznetsov, O.I. Kuznetsova, N.D. Levitov, A.O. Prokhorov, Yu.E. Sosnovikova, V.A. Semichenko.

The **purpose** of the study is to identify the groups of pupils' mental states in different educational situations according to their level of hubristic motivation.

Research sample. 321 junior schoolchildren (students of grades 1-4 of the gymnasium №169 of Kharkiv and the secondary school № 140 of Kharkiv) competed for the research.

The study of the type of hubristic motivation in junior schoolchildren was carried out with the author's projective method of studying hubristic motivation for junior pupils [4] and a short list of mental states for studying the course of various situations of educational activities of schoolchildren. Students evaluated their own psycho-emotional states in the following situations: 1) when the teacher praises for good work at a lesson; 2) when the student lost in the game,

in which he was usually the winner; 3) when student has received a lower rating for control work than expected; 4) when he has won a difficult competition.

Discussion. The specificity of the basic situations of educational activity of students is expressed not only in the concrete assortment of classes, actualized in connection with one or another educational task, but also in the proximity (or vice versa, remoteness) of interconnections between the states. "Distance" between states can serve as the basis for the formation of their taxonomic groups. Mental states in their expression in one or another situation of educational activity are grouped together. Each object of such a group is more closely connected with other objects of its group than with the objects of other groups [2].

The purpose of our empirical research was to determine the structure of the emotional states of junior pupils with different types of hubristic motivation. The structure of emotional states in junior schoolchildren in situations of success and failure within the framework of conducting (training) activities and gaming activities have been identified using hierarchical clustering. On the basis of the Euclidean distance with the construction of dendrograms, reflecting the results of the classification of emotional states by their sequential association (agglomeration), the group features the structuring of emotions have been revealed depending on the variables relevant to our study (different situations of activity).

The specificity of success and failure in the activity is expressed not only in the concrete range of the actualized emotional states, but also in the proximity / remoteness of the interconnections between the states. "Distance" between states can serve as the basis for the formation of taxonomic groups of emotional states. Emotions that are actualized in different situations are grouped together, and each object of such a group is more closely connected with other objects of its group than with objects of other groups. Realizing this part of our study, we examined the assumption that the psychological specificity of the four situations of educational and game activity (success and failure) is subjectively reflected in the tightness of links between individual states, in their groups, number and meaningful content. The structure of the dendrograms of classes, which are manifested in younger students in all situations of success and failure included all 14 categories.

Figure 1 shows the cluster structure of the emotional states of junior schoolchildren in a situation where they are praised by a teacher for good work (the situation of the success of learning activity). The structure of emotional states is represented by two clusters, each of which contains two subclusters.

The structure of the first cluster indicates the organization of emotional states in the functional system intended for mental regulation of educational activity in a situation of success (teacher's praise for good work in the class).

Fig. 1. The structure of the emotional states of junior schoolchildren in a situation where the teacher praises them for good work.

This cluster has absorbed 64,3% of all the concepts that have been clustering and thematically covers two specific classes of states – emotions of joy, enthusiasm, sense of happiness, fun (the first subcluster "joy – admiration") and a sense of certainty and calm ("confidence - pride"). Thus, in the structure of the first cluster there is a subsystem of emotional states that have a pronounced positive modality and reflect the joy, fun and pride that accompany the disciples in the teacher's praise situation. This is – good mood and happiness (joy, happiness, fun), and the experience of feelings of pride ("confidence", "admiration"), and signs of "unexpected reward" ("amazement" "interest").

The second cluster in this dendrogram appeared less voluminous (covering 35,7% of the categories) and was called "fear - boredom." The structure of the second cluster includes the emotional states of negative modality, which in this situation are oppressed. The cluster is formed by the combination of "fear", "sadness", "anger", "envy" and "boredom."

Table 1 shows the differences in the manifestation of emotional states in the situation of teacher's praise in pupils with different levels of hubristic motivation. Students with a moderate level of hubristic motivation, in which the desires for perfection and superiority are almost equal in proportion, are characterized by a high manifestation of the states of joy, fun, amazement, calmness, happiness, interest and admiration. Analyzing the average rates of the indicators of emotional states of positive modality (which generally fluctuate in the

range of the two highest scores), as well as negative modality (which do not reach two points), one can conclude that the situation of praise activates a favorable emotional background for the successful pursuit of educational activity in pupils with moderate hubristic motivation.

Table 1

Indicators of emotional states in junior pupils with different levels of hubristic motivation in a situation where the teacher praises for good work

Emotional states	Groups				H	p
	Moderate	The domination of the aspiration for perfection	The domination of the aspiration for superiority	Low hubristic motivation		
Joy	4,42±0,89	4,27±1,18	4,69±0,61	3,87±1,10	15,97	0,001
Fear	1,91±0,53	1,14±1,53	1,69±1,69	3,35±1,15	32,20	0,0001
Sadness	1,30±0,43	0,73±1,43	0,92±0,39	1,83±1,53	15,92	0,001
Anger	1,06±0,66	0,55±0,45	0,62±0,84	1,48±1,44	21,39	0,0001
Envy	0,91±0,19	0,13±0,35	1,00±0,18	1,65±1,30	45,20	0,0001
Boredom	1,24±0,77	0,68±0,19	1,77±0,86	1,65±1,30	18,68	0,001
Fun	4,49±0,70	4,05±1,30	4,54±1,35	3,22±1,73	36,35	0,001
Amazement	3,64±1,37	3,09±1,74	3,85±1,67	3,65±0,98	14,27	0,001
Calmness	3,73±1,73	2,86±2,11	4,08±1,39	3,04±1,33	21,50	0,0001
Happiness	4,24±1,08	4,50±0,95	4,69±0,83	3,52±0,99	37,11	0,0001
Confidence	3,79±1,30	4,00±1,09	4,46±0,75	2,91±1,20	31,82	0,0001
Interest	4,06±1,13	3,00±1,74	3,77±1,26	2,83±1,27	31,92	0,0001
Pride	3,55±1,58	2,36±1,98	3,92±1,15	2,57±1,65	31,68	0,0001
Admiration	4,00±1,24	3,96±1,30	4,62±1,08	3,57±1,27	29,47	0,0001

In pupils with a dominant desire for perfection in the situation of teacher's praise the state of joy, fun, happiness, and confidence are active. These students express the states of envy, anger, boredom and sorrow to a lesser extent. The teacher's praise situation activates a favorable emotional background for the learning of the lesson and new academic achievements for the pupils with a desire for perfection.

Pupils with predominance of desire for superiority are characterized by the highest rates of joy, fun, calmness, confidence, pride and admiration compared to other classes of students. The situation of praise activates the sthenic emotional states of positive modality in those subjects of educational activity,

which differ in dominance of the desire for superiority in the structure of the hubristic motivation. The desire for superiority over others can cause more violent emotional reactions in the situation of success in the educational activities of junior students. Teacher's praise in the presence of other students is a special distinction, the highest score of achievements, which is of particular importance to a junior student who seeks to excel. The high level of manifestation of the emotional state of pride as a reaction to the teacher's praise is a sign of a desire for superiority over others in schoolchildren.

Students with a low level of hubristic motivation are characterized by a statistically lower level of expressiveness of emotional states of joy, fun, calmness, confidence, interest, pride and admiration. The teacher's praise situation confuses this category of junior pupils. The emotional states of these students are polarized - they are manifested in a combination of fear with joy, astonishment and happiness, a high degree of anger and envy. We can conclude that the low level of volatile motivation determines the least favorable for achieving the goal of educational activity, an ensemble of emotional states.

Figure 2 shows the structure of the emotional states of junior schoolchildren in the situation of failure in gaming activities, namely the loss in the game, in which the student previously had success.

Fig. 2. Structure of emotional states of junior pupils in a situation of losing in the game.

The dendrogram of emotional states is represented by two clusters - "joy - calmness" and "fear - amazement". The first cluster embraced the emotional

states of "joy", "happiness", "fun", "admiration", "pride", "confidence", "interest" and "calmness", and the second cluster – the states of "fear", "sadness", "anger", "envy", "boredom" and "amazement".

In the structure of the first cluster, the predominance of the state of "pride" (which may be caused by the failure of the situation) is obvious. Within the second cluster, the states of "fear" and "sadness" are clearly manifested, a sub-cluster is very significant, created by the states of "anger" and "envy". The condition for the junior pupils in the situation is "amazement" (because the loss in the favorite game is unexpected for the subject of gaming activity).

The next task of investigation was to determine the extent of the influence of the hubristic motivation on the emotional conditions experienced by junior pupils in the situation of failures in game. The differences in their manifestation in different categories of subjects have been studied (Table 2).

Table 2

Indicators of emotional states in junior pupils with different levels of hubristic motivation in a situation of losing in the game

Emotional states	Groups				H	p
	Moderate	The domination of the aspiration for perfection	The domination of the aspiration for superiority	Low hubristic motivation		
Joy	1,73±0,73	1,36±0,44	2,09±0,89	1,04±0,17	8,53	0,05
Fear	1,45±0,52	1,45±0,68	2,18±0,81	1,84±0,34	11,42	0,01
Sadness	2,14±1,90	2,23±0,79	2,64±0,83	2,44±0,87	4,52	-
Anger	1,34±0,78	1,23±0,66	1,73±0,77	1,68±0,80	6,62	-
Enger	1,42±0,67	1,09±0,63	1,64±0,62	0,80±0,58	5,98	-
Boredom	1,54±1,03	0,82±0,16	1,64±0,44	1,68±0,70	10,61	0,01
Fun	2,13±0,78	1,45±0,54	2,45±1,32	1,96±0,74	9,45	0,05
Amazement	2,91±0,89	3,14±0,67	3,45±1,31	2,84±1,14	5,69	-
Calmness	3,03±0,81	2,23±0,82	3,00±2,01	2,52±0,96	10,06	0,05
Happiness	2,43±0,85	1,27±0,29	2,55±0,94	1,60±0,61	27,64	0,0001
Confidence	2,72±0,74	2,68±1,73	2,91±0,99	2,44±0,66	2,07	-
Interest	2,72±0,88	2,59±1,68	3,27±1,82	1,88±0,76	14,15	0,01
Pride	1,92±0,86	0,95±0,27	2,64±0,78	0,68±0,11	44,87	0,0001
Admiration	2,40±0,95	1,32±0,59	2,45±1,32	0,68±0,19	22,51	0,0001

Junior schoolchildren with moderate, volatile motivation differ in the highest levels of rest in comparison with other student groups. They exceed the

students with the dominance of the desire for perfection in terms of boredom ($t=3,00, p<0,01$), fun ($t = 2,87, p <0.01$), calmness ($t = 3,17, p < 0,01$), happiness ($t = 5,03, p<0,0001$), pride ($t = 4,23, p <0,0001$), admiration ($t=4,26, p <0,0001$). Consequently, pupils with domination of the aspiration for perfection are less calm and happy in the situation of losing in the game, while the moderate intensity of hubristic aspirations causes calmness and positive emotional background in the situation of losing in the favorite game.

Junior pupils with a predominance of desire for superiority in the structure of a hubristic motivation differ from schoolchildren with a predominance of a desire for perfection by higher level of joy ($t=2,86, p<0,01$), fear ($t=2,18, p<0,01$), envy ($t=2,22, p<0,01$), boredom ($t=4,15, p<0,0001$), fun ($t=3,36, p<0,001$), calmness ($t=2,26, p<0,01$), happiness ($t=5,12, p<0,0001$), interest ($t=2,57, p<0,01$), pride ($t=7,27, p<0,0001$), amazement ($t=3,28, p<0,001$).

The emotional ground of the situation of losing in the game is most often observed in junior schoolchildren with the predominance of desire for superior. The desire to be better than others causes them to lose much of the actualization of states of anxiety, exaltation, activating a sense of pride and envy.

Fig. 3. Structure of emotional conditions of junior pupils in the situation of obtaining lower than expected assessment for control work.

Pupils with low hubristic motivation are inferior to students with moderate hubristic motivation ($t = 3,22, p <0,01$) and students with a predominance of

aspiration for superiority ($t = 5,20, p < 0,0001$) by the indicators of pride. Compared with pupils with predominant of the desire for superiority, they tend to show a lower level of envy ($t = -2,52, p < 0,01$), joy ($t = -2,63, p < 0,01$), amazement ($t = -2,12, p < 0,05$), happiness ($t = -2,23, p < 0,01$), interest ($t = -3,39, p < 0,001$), admiration ($t = -3,76, p < 0,001$). Consequently, the low level of volatile motivation in junior students causes a lesser manifestation of pride and jealousy.

Figure 3 shows the structure of psycho-emotional states of pupils in the situation of obtaining lower than expected estimates for control work, which is represented by two clusters. The first cluster is a monolithic group of positive emotions of joy, happiness, fun, pride and admiration. The cluster is smaller in scope and is characterized by 35,7% of the categories.

Table 3

Indicators of emotional states in junior pupils with different levels of hubristic motivation in a situation of obtaining lower than expected assessment for control work

Emotional states	Groups				H	p
	Moderate	The domination of the aspiration for perfection	The domination of the aspiration for superiority	Low hubristic motivation		
Joy	1,19±0,57	1,10±0,42	1,54±0,88	1,05±0,24	1,21	-
Fear	2,64±0,82	1,61±0,84	2,38±1,51	2,81±1,12	22,74	0,0001
Sadness	3,11±1,67	2,47±0,71	2,46±0,88	3,33±1,24	12,23	0,01
Anger	1,64±0,94	0,87±0,39	1,23±0,49	1,48±0,57	8,90	0,05
Enger	1,75±0,79	1,56±0,64	2,23±0,64	2,24±1,34	6,60	-
Boredom	1,42±0,97	0,87±0,48	1,46±0,71	1,86±1,35	12,29	0,01
Fun	1,22±0,67	1,15±0,67	1,54±1,08	1,48±0,63	0,95	-
Amazement	3,28±1,68	3,08±1,42	2,92±1,66	2,71±1,19	4,94	-
Calmness	2,25±0,97	2,67±0,92	3,08±1,83	2,57±1,83	6,56	-
Hapiness	1,58±0,82	0,94±0,39	1,77±1,17	1,52±0,60	10,56	0,01
Confidence	3,06±1,85	2,13±0,62	2,46±0,88	1,00±0,77	31,74	0,0001
Interest	2,47±0,78	2,23±0,74	3,23±1,73	2,76±1,41	11,10	0,01
Pride	1,69±1,00	0,77±0,33	1,62±0,71	0,90±0,33	14,14	0,01
Admiration	1,53±0,84	1,14±0,73	1,62±1,00	1,33±0,39	4,98	-

The second cluster contains two subcluster: the first one is represented by anger, boredom, envy, sadness, surprise and fear, that is characterized by a set

of psycho-emotional states that does not coincide with the purpose of educational activity. The second subcluster of the second cluster contains confidence and interest.

Table 3 shows the psycho-emotional states of schoolchildren with different types of hubristic motivation in the situation of obtaining lower than expected estimates for control work.

Junior pupils with predominance of desire for superior are characterized by higher envy ($t = 2,42, p < 0,05$), pride ($t = 3,39, p < 0,0001$), fear ($t = 2,64, p < 0,01$), boredom ($t = 2,21, p < 0,05$) and other states in a situation of obtaining a lower rating than pupils with a domination of the desire for perfection. Students with low level of hubristic motivation have lower levels of confidence ($t = -3,08, p < 0,0001$) and higher fear ($t = 2,89, p < 0,01$) and sadness ($t = 2,19, p < 0,05$) than pupils with a predominance of desire for perfection. Consequently, the domination of the desire for perfection in the structure of the hubristic motivation has a beneficial effect on the course of emotional states of pupils in a situation of failure in educational activities.

Figure 4 shows the structure of emotional states of students in a situation of success in competitions.

Fig. 4. Structure of emotional states of junior pupils in a situation of winning in competition.

The first cluster (64,2% of the categories) was created by states of positive modality ("joy - interest"). A smaller cluster combines less pronounced states of

fear, sadness, anger, envy and boredom. Compared to other situations of success and failure, the situation of success in a game is characterized by more positive emotional states for junior students.

Table 4 shows the differences in the manifestation of the psycho-emotional states of junior pupils with varying levels of hubristic motivation in a victory situation in competitions.

Table 4

Indicators of emotional states in junior pupils with different levels of hubristic motivation in a situation of the win in a competition

Emotional states	Groups				H	p
	Moderate	The domination of the aspiration for perfection	The domination of the aspiration for superiority	Low hubristic motivation		
Joy	4,86±0,48	4,77±0,52	4,92±0,27	4,24±0,75	53,51	0,0001
Fear	1,47±0,68	1,23±0,90	1,62±0,79	0,30±0,11	13,06	0,01
Sadness	0,56±0,93	0,50±0,08	0,62±0,15	0,30±0,09	12,44	0,01
Anger	0,47±0,13	0,39±0,09	0,77±0,43	0,50±0,07	17,65	0,001
Enger	0,56±0,19	0,14±0,06	0,78±0,32	0,60±0,15	25,54	0,0001
Boredom	0,69±0,40	0,19±0,09	0,62±0,15	0,50±0,23	20,21	0,001
Fun	4,31±1,47	4,55±0,73	4,62±0,93	3,42±2,06	15,96	0,01
Amazement	4,03±1,49	3,82±1,74	4,00±1,37	4,27±1,31	3,91	-
Calmness	3,42±1,56	3,36±1,79	3,23±1,90	3,94±1,71	6,33	-
Hapiness	4,47±1,02	4,77±0,60	4,69±0,83	4,42±0,87	9,47	0,05
Confidence	4,31±1,05	4,23±1,09	3,85±1,41	4,00±1,22	6,35	-
Interest	3,11±1,70	3,36±1,62	3,87±1,43	0,30±0,17	75,02	0,0001
Pride	3,42±1,73	3,82±1,65	4,22±1,34	1,45±1,15	61,91	0,01
Admiration	4,19±1,42	4,64±0,78	4,46±1,40	4,64±0,70	8,40	0,05

Pupils with a predominance of desire for superiority show higher values of pride in winning situations than students with moderate levels of hubristic motivation ($t = 3,55$; $p < 0,001$) and low level of hubristic motivation ($t = 10,37$; $p < 0,0001$). The expressed desire for superiority is determined by the higher indexes of interest ($t = 14,02$; $p < 0,0001$), fun ($t = 4,20$; $p < 0,0001$), envy ($t = 3,41$; $p < 0,0001$), anger ($t = 3,07$; $p < 0,01$), sadness ($t = 3,05$; $p < 0,01$), fear ($t = 4,11$; $p < 0,0001$) and joy ($t = 7,04$; $p < 0,0001$) than students with low level of hubristic motivation. Pupils with a predominance of desire for perfection have higher scores for joy ($t = 2,19$; $p < 0,05$), fear ($t = 2,73$; $p < 0,01$), sadness ($t = 2,64$; $p < 0,01$), fun ($t = 3,96$; $p < 0,001$), happiness ($t = 2,33$; $p < 0,05$), interest ($t =$

= 10,59; $p < 0,0001$), pride ($t = 7,36$; $p < 0,05$) than students with low level of hubristic motivation.

Consequently, the high degree of hubristic aspirations causes more pronounced emotional states in the situation of success in gaming activities.

Conclusions. Hubristic motivation at junior school age is a factor of the emotional states in situations of success and failure in educational and gaming activities. The situation of winning in a game is the basis of the course of most positive emotional states for children in general. The predominance of desire for superiority influences on the states of happiness, joy and confidence in situations of praise. The desire for superiority also activates states of fear, sadness, anger, envy and amazement in a situation of losing in the game. The failure of the educational activity negatively affects the emotional states in the situation of winning the competition and has positive influence on emotional states both of the pupils with predominance of the desire for superiority and perfection.

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